

INITIATION AND PROPAGATION OF FIBER FAILURE IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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Keywords: *strength, fiber failure, phantom nodes, XFEM, statistical scaling*

1 Introduction

Fiber failure in the laminated composite materials is the ultimate catastrophic mode of failure. It is often precipitated by matrix damage such as cracking and delamination which has a significant effect on both initiation and propagation of fiber failure. Availability and rapid increase of computer power has enabled recent successes in the development of the discrete damage modeling (DDM) technique [1]-[3], which is based on the direct simulation of displacement discontinuities associated with individual instances of matrix cracking occurring inside the composite plies, and delaminations at the interfaces between the plies. On the other hand, a Weibull distribution has been found to well describe the size effect of the fiber direction tensile strength in unidirectional composites, as shown in Ref. [4],[5]. It has also been shown in the above references, that the application of the Weibull integral approach to fiber failure prediction, in conjunction with the matrix cracking and delamination modeling in laminated composites, is capable of predicting open hole strength in a range of hole sizes and stacking sequences in quasi-isotropic laminates. However, these methods were applied in situations when initiation of the fiber macro-failure coincided with the final failure of the composite coupon, and were not extended to simulate the fiber failure progression. Continuum damage mechanics (CDM) methods, however, offer a framework to perform progressive failure simulation in the fiber direction, albeit not including the statistical nature of fiber failure mechanism in the consideration at all. In the present paper we will apply the two approaches, CDM and Weibull integral, to open hole strength prediction in quasi-isotropic laminates in conjunction with DDM.

2 Damage Modeling

2.1 Matrix cracking and Delamination

The DDM approach consists of mesh-independent modeling of matrix cracks in each ply of the laminate, and modeling the delamination between the plies by using a cohesive formulation at the ply interface. The matrix cracks are modeled by using the regularized MIC formulation [1]-[3], termed Rx-FEM. The regularized formulation deals with continuous enrichment functions, and replaces the Heaviside step function with continuous function changing from 0 to 1 over a narrow volume of the so called gradient zone. The formalism tying the volume integrals in the gradient zone to surface integrals in the limit of mesh refinement was discussed in [1] and [3]. The simulation begins without any initial matrix cracks, which then are inserted based on a failure criterion during the simulation. The LaRC03 [6] failure criterion is chosen in the present work. The propagation of each MIC is performed by using cohesive zone formulation [7]. Note that the delamination between the plies is facilitated by using cohesive zone elements preinstalled on each ply interface and is simulated by using the same cohesive zone formulation [7]. A schematic of the process is shown in Fig. 1. After the failure criterion is met at a certain location a matrix crack is added by using Rx-FEM. Next, the load is increased and the program enters a nonlinear iteration step at which the cohesive zone model associated with the inserted crack(s) is opened. After convergence is achieved the failure criterion is checked again for new crack insertion. At the same time the fiber failure criterion is checked. In the case of the Weibull-based statistical criteria (Critical Failure Volume – CFV), described in the next section, we check for final failure. If failure is not

predicted, the load is increased and the computation continues. If failure is predicted, the simulation is stopped and the current load level recorded as failure load. This corresponds to the left branch in Fig. 1. In the case of progressive fiber failure, also presented in the next section, the computations continue until the specimen stops carrying the applied load. In this case the element properties are degraded and new equilibrium obtained in the process of nonlinear iterations.

Fig. 1. Solution algorithm

2.2 Fiber Failure Simulation

A. Critical Failure Volume method

Volumetric scaling of the fiber direction strength is experimentally verified to follow the Weibull distribution as following:

$$f(\sigma, V) = 1 - e^{-\frac{V}{V_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\beta}\right)^\alpha} \quad (1)$$

where α and β are the Weibull parameters defining the scatter and mean of the distribution, V and V_0 are the specimen volume and the control volume

respectively, and σ is the fiber direction stress. The idea of the CFV method is to apply scaling, as in Eqn. (1), to various subregions of the composite with nonuniform stress field and find the subregion with the maximum failure probability. Two considerations are required to achieve this goal. First, one needs to define the probability of failure for a volume with nonuniform stress distribution, and second, develop a procedure for the systematic search of the subvolumes. The assumption, which we will use to evaluate the probability of failure in the nonuniformly loaded regions, states that Eqn. (1) provides a lower bound of probability of failure of a specimen with nonuniform stress distribution, if the stress in each point is higher or equal to σ . Thus the probability of failure P of a nonuniformly stressed specimen with stress distribution $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$ can be estimated as:

$$P \geq f(\sigma_u, V), \quad (2)$$

if

$$\sigma_u = \min_{\mathbf{x} \in V} (\sigma(\mathbf{x})). \quad (3)$$

The idea of the search for the most likely failure subvolume is to parameterize the entire volume of interest by introducing a function $v(\sigma)$, which is equal to the volume of the material, which has a fiber direction stress higher than σ , $\sigma < \sigma_M$ and σ_M is the maximum value of stress in the entire coupon. We will assume that σ_M is finite. By substituting the function $v(\sigma)$ into Eqn. (1) one arrives at:

$$f(\sigma) = 1 - e^{-\frac{v(\sigma)}{V_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\beta}\right)^\alpha} \quad (4)$$

which allows to compute the probability of failure for any overstressed subvolume. In most cases, the maximum stress value is achieved at some point, i.e. $v(\sigma_M) = 0$ therefore $f(\sigma_M) = 0$. The critical failure volume by definition is then defined by a stress contour σ_c such that

$$f(\sigma_c) = \max f(\sigma) \text{ for all } \sigma < \sigma_M \quad (5)$$

We refer the reader for more details to references[10][11] for existence of $f(\sigma_c)$, which we will further denote as $f_c = f(\sigma_c)$. Note [11] that if the volume $v(\sigma_c)$ has an in-plane dimension $l_c = \sqrt{v(\sigma_c)/h}$, which is on the order of Rosen's characteristic length δ ; then the maximum value in Eqn.(5) is taken not over all stress values, but is limited to stress values such that $v(\sigma)$ has corresponding dimensions $l_c > 6\delta$.

In the original CFV concept, it is assumed that f_c is the probability of failure of the entire specimen because if a finite subvolume suffers fiber failure; then it was assumed that the entire specimen cannot sustain anymore load. The remaining question is selecting the value for probability of failure for computing the failure load. A common approach in this case is not assigning a specific value of the probability of failure, but instead computing the value of f_c so that the applied load is equal to the average failure load for the Weibull distribution, i.e.

$$(-\ln(1 - f_c))^{-1/\alpha} \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{\alpha}\right) = 1 \quad (6)$$

Thus the failure load is defined as the applied load at which the failure probability f_c of CFV satisfies Eqn. (6).

B. Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM)

Fiber failure is the only damage mode simulated by using CDM in the present work, so that the stiffness tensor at a given stress level is defined as $C=(1-d)C_0$, where C_0 is the initial stiffness. The damage variable, d , is defined based on the stress strain relationship proposed in Maimi et al. [8],[9] and is shown in Fig. 2. Determination of the numerical values of the parameters defining the cohesive curve in Fig. 2 for IM7/8552 material system used in the present analysis including the fracture toughness, $G_{XT}=81.5$ N/mm and coefficients $f_{XT}=0.2$, $f_{GT}=0.4$ as well as the characteristic length, has been addressed in[9]. The initiation stress value, X_t , represents the fiber direction strength measured on standard unidirectional coupon type tests. This value depends on the volume of the coupon and for IM7/8552 follows the Weibull distribution with the modulus of $\alpha=40$. Thus the specific value used for

simulation with CDM is not entirely defined. In our simulations, we will use three values of the failure initiation strength: reduced $X_t=2.4$ GPa, nominal $X_t=2.82$ GPa obtained for a typical 8-ply unidirectional coupon with total volume of $V_0=1946$ mm³ and adjusted $X_t=3.4$ GPa, which is the nominal strength that has been scaled for a 1mm³ of stressed volume.

Fig. 2. Schematic of the Uniaxial Response in Longitudinal Tension in the Fiber Direction Described in Maimi et al. [8]

PROBLEM STATEMENT AND MATERIAL PROPERTIES

An open hole coupon with central 6.35 mm diameter hole is considered. The length in x – direction is equal to 152 mm, the width in y direction is 38 mm and each ply is 0.127 mm thick in z-direction. Tensile loading in the x-direction is applied by incrementing the displacement u_x at the edges $x=0,L$, so that

$$u_x^i(0,y,z) = u_x^{i-1}(0,y,z) - \Delta^i \quad \text{and} \quad u_x^i(L,y,z) = u_x^{i-1}(L,y,z) + \Delta^i \quad (7)$$

where Δ^i is a constant and i is the loading step number. Such incremental formulation is required to properly account for the thermal curing stresses prior to the mechanical loading. The displacement field u_x^0 appearing in equation (7) is computed by solving a thermal-mechanical expansion problem under boundary

conditions which simulate free expansion and only restrict rigid body motion, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} u_x^0(0,0,0)=0, u_y^0(0,W,0)=0 \text{ and} \\ u_z^0(x,y,0)=0. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The incremental loading boundary conditions (7) are supplemented with constraint conditions on the other displacement components at the lateral edges $x=0$ and L , so that

$$\begin{aligned} u_y^i(0,y,z)=u_y^0(0,y,z) \text{ and } u_y^i(L,y,z)= \\ u_y^0(L,y,z), \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} u_z^i(0,y,z)=u_z^0(0,y,z) \text{ and } u_z^i(L,y,z)= \\ u_z^0(L,y,z), \end{aligned}$$

Unidirectional ply properties used for analysis are shown in Tables I, II and III. These properties were used for baseline strength predictions and as the average values for random spatial variation.

TABLE I. NOMINAL UNIDIRECTIONAL STIFFNESS AND STRENGTH PROPERTIES FOR IM7/5250-4

E_1	165	GPa
	10.3	GPa
G_{12}	5.79	GPa
G_{23}	3.31	GPa
ν_{12}	0.31	
ν_{23}	0.56	
Y_t	66	MPa
S	123	MPa
Y_c	248	MPa

TABLE II. PROPERTIES USED IN COHESIVE

LAW		
K	2.71E+8	N / mm ³
G_{1c}	0.225	N / mm
G_{2c}	0.6225	N / mm
Y_t	66	MPa
S	122	MPa

TABLE III. PROPERTIES USED FOR FIBER FAILURE PREDICTION

X_T	2.827	GPa
V_0	1966	mm ³
α	40	
l_c	0.266	mm

3. Results and Discussion

A. Critical Failure Volume Criterion Based Predictions

Simulations were performed by using an in-house software called the B-spline Analysis Method (BSAM) [12] where the Rx-FEM methodology is implemented, with meshes generated by Abaqus/CAE. In all simulation cases in the present manuscript the load displacement curve was linear up to fiber failure. Fig. 3 shows the load displacement curve for laminates A ([45/0/-45/90]_s) and B ([0/45/90/-45]_s). The solid and dotted gray lines on the same figure show the fiber failure loads corresponding to the probability of fiber failure in Eqn. (6) for the two laminates respectively. As explained earlier, the laminate failure occurs when the applied load becomes equal to the fiber failure load. At applied load of approximately 350 MPa the fiber failure load in the two laminates is approximately the same and slightly over 500 MPa. It means that if the state of matrix damage was frozen and the load increased to 500 MPa both laminates would fail at the same load level. As can be seen, with further increase in the applied load and subsequent matrix damage evolution, the fiber

failure loads for the two laminates diverge and that for the “B” laminate becomes considerably higher.

The tensile strength prediction results are summarized in Table IV. While the weaker laminate simulation is slightly above one standard deviation from the mean, the stronger laminate simulation is very close to the experimental mean strength value. Snap shots of matrix damage distribution at the applied load level of 350 MPa at which the matrix damage starts affecting the fiber failure and at the load level corresponding to failure for the two laminates are shown in Fig. 4. The snapshots show dominance of 90° and -45° matrix cracking in “A” and “B” laminates respectively, which is explained by double thickness of the respective plies at the mid-surface and their subsequent higher propensity to matrix cracking, which is captured by fracture mechanics nature of DDM simulation. In Fig. 5 the close up images of damage patterns at 414 MPa and 508 MPa for “A” and

Fig. 3. Traction-Displacement Curve with CFV predictions

Fig. 4. Predicted matrix damage in uniform material properties simulations at (a),(c) CFV initiation point and (b),(d) failure load of the quasi-isotropic laminates

Fig. 5. Comparison between experimental and simulated damage patterns for the two laminates at 414 MPa (a-b) and 508MPa (c-d).

”B” laminates are compared with planer X-Ray images from Ref. [11]. The following color scheme is used for delaminations in “A” and “B” laminates respectively, brown: 45/0 and 0/45; green 0/-45 and 45/90; and blue -45/90 and 90/-45. In both cases the delaminations are highly localized near the hole edge, however the extent of simulated delamination is larger than seen in the experiment. A critical factor contributing to fiber direction stress redistribution near the hole edge is the splitting in the 0° plies. The predicted length of splits is very consistent with experiment. Note that the images of splits in the “A” laminate simulation are mostly covered by the shading of delamination at the 45/0 interface. However, the

difference in length between the splits in the two laminates is clearly seen and matches the experiment well.

TABLE IV: CFV PREDICTION OF TENSILE STRENGTH (MPa)

Layup	Experiment[11]	Simulation
[45/0/-45/90] _s	468.5 ± 3.9%	492
[0/45/90/-45] _s	560.7 ± 5.6%	559

B. Continuum Damage Mechanics Based Predictions.

The results of strength prediction in the “A” and “B” laminates by using progressive fiber failure analysis combined with CDM are shown in Table V and Fig. 6 and 7 respectively. The CDM predictions

Fig. 6. “A” laminate strength predicted by using CDM with different initiation stress values

TABLE V: CDM PREDICTION OF TENSILE STRENGTH (MPa)

Initiation Strength X_t	[45/0/-45/90] _s “A”	[0/45/90/-45] _s “B”
2.4	441	448
2.87	448	470
3.4	458	478

Fig. 7. “B” laminate strength predicted by using CDM with different initiation stress values

exhibit remarkable independence from the initiation stress, which is an important characteristic of the model. Note that the propagation parameters, such as the fracture toughness G_{XT} and parameters f_{XT} and f_{GT} were used the same as in [8] obtained for IM7/8552 material. The strength values predicted for the “A” laminate are also very close to experimental. What is different, however, is the significant under prediction of the strength in “B” laminates. The “B” laminate strength is very close to that of “A” laminates, which contradicts experimental data. A possible explanation of this disagreement is in the interaction of progressive fiber failure and DDM and specifically the load levels at which the matrix damage occurs in comparison to fiber failure. The splitting and delamination, which delay the fiber failure takes place at loads very close to final failure as seen on Fig. 3. Indeed for the “B” laminate the stress relief does not occur before 500MPa. The load levels at which the initiation stress is exceeded in the CDM analysis are significantly lower and therefore create the possibility of having a “fiber pre-crack” which will propagate regardless of the stress relief. A variant of CDM with statistical scaling of initial strength is suggested to alleviate this problem.

4. Conclusions

A finite element method and software implementing Rx-FEM approach and allowing modeling of complex interactive networks of matrix cracks and

delaminations are developed. The regularized formulation preserves the element Gauss integration schema for arbitrary cracking direction, and allows straightforward connections between neighboring plies with different orientations of properties and cracks. A cohesive zone method is used to predict the matrix cracking and delamination evolution. Ply level stiffness, strength, and fracture toughness properties measured in independent experiments are the only properties required for analysis.

Strength prediction by using CFV statistical final failure criterion and progressive continuum damage mechanics criterion in combination with Rx-FEM discrete modeling of matrix damage was performed for two quasi-isotropic laminates. The CFV based prediction showed reasonable correlation with experimental data for both laminates. It appeared to capture the effect of the stress relief in fiber direction due to matrix damage. The CDM based prediction showed remarkable agreement with experimental data for laminate “A” where the matrix damage was expected to have less effect on fiber failure. It, however, did not predict the notable difference in the strength of the two laminates. A possible combination of the statistical scaling of initial strength in CDM is recommended.

Acknowledgments

The work was funded under NASA AAD-2 contract number NNX08AB05A-G and AFRL Contract number FA8650-10-D-5011.

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